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Energy Market Manipulation via False-Data Injection Attacks

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ABSTRACT Locational Marginal Prices (LMPs) are critical indicators in modern energy markets, representing the cost of delivering electricity at specific locations while considering the generation and transmission constraints. LMPs facilitate the transition to dynamic energy markets by providing real-time pricing signals that reflect supply and demand conditions, thereby incentivizing efficient resource allocation and encouraging investments in renewable energy sources. However, determining LMPs requires the processing of vast amounts of data, including real-time electricity demand, generation capacities, transmission line statuses, and market bids. Owing to vulnerabilities in the underlying sensors and communication infrastructure, adversaries can launch profit-driven stealthy False Data Injection Attacks (FDIAs) to manipulate LMPs. Such manipulations can have severe consequences, including inflated electricity prices, reduced market efficiency, distorted competition, and hindered integration of renewable energy sources. Although several studies have examined the operational consequences of FDIAs, their financial impact on energy market outcomes remains insufficiently explored. This work presents a comprehensive review of FDIAs aimed at manipulating LMPs, a key pricing mechanism in modern energy markets. A detailed analysis was conducted to identify vulnerabilities arising from both the energy system infrastructure and market operations. In addition, existing energy market threat models and defense mechanisms are systematically reviewed. Finally, key research gaps are identified, and future research directions are outlined to enhance the resilience of energy markets against FDIA threats.

INDEX TERMS Locational Marginal Prices (LMPs), False Data Injection Attacks (FDIAs), energy markets, market manipulation, cybersecurity, Smart Grid, State Estimation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electrical Power Systems (EPSs) have undergone a significant transformation with a shift towards greener energy solutions, leading to the development of smart grids. This transition has resulted in the increased integration of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), such as wind turbines and solar power, which alter both the operational and market dynamics of energy systems. In addition to these technological advancements, energy markets have evolved from simple supplier-retailer-customer models to competitive frameworks, where market participants actively bid and offer energy within dynamic pools. Locational Marginal Prices (LMPs) have emerged as a key mechanism for determining the market dynamics in modern energy systems. LMPs represent the cost of delivering electricity at different locations within a

transmission grid, reflecting the marginal costs of generation, grid congestion, and transmission losses [1], [2].

A. MOTIVATION

LMPs are essential to ensure efficient resource allocation and market operations. However, they are vulnerable to manipulation, particularly through False Data Injection Attacks (FDIA), which exploit weaknesses in the grid's Information and Communication Technology (ICT) infrastructure. FDIA involves injecting false data into the system to deceive state estimation processes, leading to inaccurate results and indirect manipulation of LMPs. This manipulation can have significant financial, operational, and stability-related consequences for the energy market. For instance, artificially inflated or deflated LMPs distort market price signals and may

cause financial losses to legitimate market participants, including consumers. Furthermore, persistent FDIA can affect grid stability by disrupting dispatch decisions, exacerbating congestion, and increasing the likelihood of grid failures.

The significance of LMP manipulation and FDIA in energy systems is not merely theoretical, as evidenced by real-world instances. One notable example is the Western U.S. energy crisis of 2001, where manipulative practices led to severe shortages in California, resulting in blackouts and the collapse of major energy companies [3]. More recently, in 2022, the Federal Energy Regulatory Commission (FERC) imposed a \$4 million penalty on a major energy company and several individuals to engage in fraudulent trading activities within the PJM energy markets [4]. Additionally, in the UK, Ofgem fined companies for market manipulation, such as false reporting capacity, which resulted in £12.8 million in illicit profits [5].

B. CONTRIBUTION

Given the growing vulnerability of energy markets to FDIA and similar attacks, there is an urgent need for a better understanding of these risks and for the development of effective countermeasures. The existing literature has made substantial progress in studying the threats posed by FDIA, especially in relation to LMP manipulation. However, comprehensive and up-to-date reviews synthesizing these findings and exploring future research directions are scarce. To the best of our knowledge, only two review papers exist on this topic: [6] and [2]. However, these reviews do not delve deeply into the technical categorization of FDIA data sources, nor do they focus specifically on LMP manipulation. Instead, they address broader cybersecurity concerns including operational and financial issues. This paper aims to fill this gap by offering a systematic review that presents a data-centric perspective on LMP manipulation via FDIA, and provides valuable insights into potential research directions for the broader research community. Table 1 provides detailed information on the methodology employed to gather review materials.

The main contributions of this review are as follows:

- A detailed background on both the energy system infrastructure and energy markets, with a particular focus on their inherent vulnerabilities to market manipulation and associated risks.
- This comprehensive systematic review provides an in-depth analysis of existing methods for LMP manipulation via FDIA and the corresponding defense mechanisms.
- Perform categorization to enhance the understanding of LMPs manipulation threat models.
- To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to conduct a thorough survey of defenses against LMP manipulations.
- Outline of challenges and future directions for the energy industry to further investigate and address LMPs manipulation challenges.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents background information on smart grids, while Section III analyzes energy market operations. Sections IV and V provide an in-depth examination of threat models and countermeasures for LMP manipulation. Section VI discusses challenges and future research directions. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper.

II. SMART GRID: AN OVERVIEW

A Smart Grid (SG) represents a transformative approach to the generation, distribution, and consumption of electrical energy. By leveraging ICT, SG significantly enhance the efficiency, reliability, and sustainability of the power grid infrastructure [8]. A defining feature of an SG is its dual communication capability. Unlike traditional power grids, which operate on a one-way communication model, SG enables bidirectional communication between various grid components. This allows for real-time data exchange, processing, knowledge derivation, localized awareness, and control commands through Internet of Things (IoT) devices along with communication technologies. The bidirectional flow of data and (contextual) information facilitates improved SG monitoring, management, and control, leading to greater operational efficiency, resilience, and faster responses to system disruptions.

The SG is driven by massive amounts of contextual data collected from various collection points within the grid, processed in real-time, and used to optimize and reconfigure the entire electrical system [9]. Real-time data and predictive analytics play a crucial role in defining SG functionality by enabling real-time and automatic processing of measurements, state inference and estimation, outage and fault detection, demand response, and voltage control and regulation [10]. However, this data-centric and analytic-driven intelligence integration in the SG introduces various cybersecurity challenges that significantly impact the stability and reliability of the SG [11]. Fig. 1 illustrates (a) the architecture of the SG, highlighting (b) the data flow and (c) the corresponding FDIA threats that originate from the lower levels, where contextual data are generated, and ascend to the upper levels, where operational and trading processes occur.

Thus, we provide insights into SG from a data science perspective, focusing on the key elements of data sources, data collection, data communication, processing, knowledge derivation, inference and data analytics. Understanding these fundamental components is essential to understand the market and threat models of energy market manipulation.

A. CONTEXTUAL DATA SOURCES

Contextual data from SGs are generated in real time at a high velocity and volume, fitting into the 5V framework of Big Data [9]. Extracting meaningful insights from SG data is crucial for SG applications, necessitating a deep understanding of its diverse sources, which encompass the entire electricity lifecycle from generation and transmission to distribution and consumption, as well as non-electric contextual data such as

TABLE 1. Methodology Overview for Systematic Literature Review

Method	Snowballing methodology [7]
Start Set Selection	<i>Keywords:</i> False Data Injection Attack, Cybersecurity Attack, Energy Market, Locational Marginal Price, Market Manipulation, Attack Detection, Anomaly Detection. <i>Databases:</i> Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore, ACM, ScienceDirect, SpringerLink.
Backward \ Forward Snowballing	References \ Citations from the selected start set were systematically examined. Papers were included if they met the inclusion criteria.
Inclusion Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directly related to FDIAs in energy markets. • Peer-reviewed paper. • Discusses FDIA's impact on LMP. • Publication range: 2011–2024.
Exclusion Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focuses only on operational FDIAs without addressing financial consequences. • Focuses only on market fraudulent practices. • Non peer-reviewed paper • Duplicate publication.
Data Extraction Focus	<p>Threat Models: Scope, attack types, vectors, and attacker knowledge requirements. Differentiation between theoretical models and practical implementations may also be examined.</p> <p>Defense Mechanisms: Type, Defense level, and analysis methods for proposed solutions. Categorisation of Defense mechanisms (e.g., prevention, detection, mitigation) may be considered.</p>

TABLE 2. Contextual Data Sources in Smart Grids

Category	Description	Examples
Generation & Consumption	Data on electricity generation and usage.	Active Power, Reactive Power, Energy Consumption, Peak Demand.
Grid Infrastructure	Smart grid operational and physical data.	Voltage, Transformer Load, Line Losses, Fault Records.
Market & Economic	Data on pricing, markets, and regulations.	Spot Prices, Tariffs, Carbon Costs, Auction Data.
External	Non-electric data influencing the grid.	Temperature, Wind Speed, Solar Irradiance, Public Holidays.

environmental conditions, demographic trends, and market dynamics. These types of data directly influence electricity-related data. Table 2 summarizes the main contextual data sources in SGs, categorizing them into four key groups: Generation & Consumption Data, covering electricity generation from various sources and consumption patterns; Smart Grid Infrastructure Data, including distribution and transmission lines, substations, and related parameters; Market & Economic Data, involving electricity markets, prices, regulatory policies, and economic indicators; and External Data, encompassing weather conditions, local holidays, and social events impacting electricity consumption and generation behavior.

B. DATA ACQUISITION

The infrastructure for data acquisition in the SG was designed to gather comprehensive data from various sources across the grid. This involves deploying IoT devices such as smart meters, Remote Terminal Units (RTUs), and Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) at strategic locations. Contextual data collected from these devices include electricity usage at residential and commercial properties and real-time (monitoring of) voltage, current, and frequency along transmission

lines. Such data acquisition devices ensure a continuous and detailed flow of contextual information from end-user sites through distribution and transmission networks, providing robust knowledge for grid management and optimization.

C. DATA TRANSMISSION

Data transmission in an SG is facilitated through a structured hierarchy of networks that enables the efficient exchange of information between devices and control centers [12], [13]. Home Area Networks (HAN) adopt protocols such as Zigbee, Z-Wave, and Wi-Fi to allow data exchange between smart IoT devices and appliances within homes, offices, or buildings, thus supporting consumers to monitor and control their energy usage. Neighborhood Area Networks (NAN) cover specific (geographical) neighborhoods or communities and employ protocols such as WiMAX, LTE, and RF mesh networks. This allows communication between smart meters, distribution automation devices, and local infrastructure by aggregating and transmitting localized contextual data. Wide-Area Networks (WAN) span larger geographical areas, connecting substations, control centers, transmission lines, and distribution networks. They often utilize protocols such as MPLS, IPSec, and fiber-optic communication. This multi-layered communication protocol ensures seamless data flow from collection points to centralized servers, enabling scalable monitoring and control of the entire SG [12], [13].

D. DATA & PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS

The most important steps in data processing and knowledge derivation within an SG are data analysis and inference. This enables the extraction of useful insights and patterns that support robust and scalable decision-making. Data and predictive analytics aims to identify hidden, potentially useful, and reusable information and trends in massive datasets and knowledge bases, transforming them into practical information and generalizable patterns. In [14], the predictive and

FIGURE 1. Overview of a) Smart Grid Architecture, b) Corresponding Data Flow, and c) General FDIA towards upper layers.

data analytics tasks in an SG were classified as event detection and identification analytics, contextual state and operational analytics, and customer analytics. Event analytics aid in diagnosing and detecting power system events such as faults, outages, and abnormal conditions, as well as identifying malicious attacks and electricity theft.

For instance, real-time fault detection Machine Learning (ML) algorithms quickly isolate and manage faults, minimizing downtime enhanced with self-healing properties. Contextual state and operational analytics involve tasks like state inference and estimation, SG topology identification, and energy forecasting. These analytics ensure efficient system operation, accurate load forecasting, and optimal resource dispatch (along with smart task offloading decision making). An example includes ML-based analytics to forecast energy demand ensuring balanced energy distribution and reducing operational costs. Customer analytics focus on ‘understanding’ and ‘interpreting’ consumer behavior and energy consumption patterns, enabling utilities to offer tailored demand response programs and improve customer classification and intelligent profiling. This involves analyzing smart meter data to identify long-/short-term consumption trends and optimize energy usage, benefiting both the utility and the customer through ‘personalized’ energy-saving recommendations and dynamic pricing strategies.

E. FDIA IN A SMART GRID

In recent decades, the energy sector has been the target of numerous high-profile cyber-physical attacks, demonstrating the susceptibility of critical infrastructures to such threats.

One of the earliest notable incidents occurred in 1982, when a cyberattack orchestrated by the CIA during the Cold War led to a devastating gas pipeline explosion in Siberia. The attackers successfully manipulated the pipeline’s control systems, triggering catastrophic failures [15]. Recently, in 2015 Ukraine has experienced a significant attack on its power grid, causing a massive blackout that affected more than 225,000 customers. Hackers breached the Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system and remotely activated circuit breakers, and left operators struggling to manually restore power [16]. These examples highlight escalating risks to the energy industry, with reports indicating a substantial increase in cyber-related disruptions. For instance, between 2011 and 2014, the United States recorded 362 power interruptions, underlining the increasing frequency and severity of these attacks [17].

The vulnerabilities of Smart Grids (SGs) are closely linked to the design and functionality of their data acquisition and transmission systems. These systems depend on a variety of Internet of Things (IoT) devices, including smart meters, RTUs, and PMUs, strategically deployed across the grid to collect real-time, detailed data [18]. These devices monitor key parameters such as electricity consumption, voltage, current, and frequency along transmission lines, enabling continuous oversight of grid operations. However, the extensive deployment of these devices introduces numerous points of vulnerabilities. If attackers gain access to these devices, they can manipulate the transmitted data, resulting in false readings that can disrupt the grid operations. This vulnerability extends to higher levels of the system, where compromised

data can have cascading effects. Moreover, the reliance on IoT devices makes the grid susceptible to weaknesses in their security protocols, such as inadequate encryption or authentication measures, which attackers can exploit to compromise the overall integrity of the system.

The consequences of cyberattacks on smart grids can be far-reaching, encompassing financial losses, power supply disruptions, and instability in grid operations. The effects on the grid stability can be particularly severe. Cyberattacks involving false data injections can lead to incorrect load shedding, unnecessary power generation rescheduling, or even large-scale blackouts [17]. A 2014 study demonstrated that spoofed GPS signals could activate protective measures, triggering load shedding and widespread instability [19]. Such attacks undermine the resilience of the power grid, potentially causing catastrophic failures if left unaddressed. Beyond the instability impact, the economic repercussions are also concerning, with attacks leading to inflated operational expenses, energy theft [20], [21], and market price manipulation [2], ultimately impacting both utility providers and their customers. For example, an FDIA targeting grid topology can obscure outages, causing operational confusion and significant financial losses [22]. In some instances, attackers have manipulated circuit breaker statuses, resulting in financial damages of up to \$100,000 per day [23].

Although energy theft is beyond the scope of this study, understanding the key differences between energy theft and LMP manipulation is essential to develop effective countermeasures against these threats. Table 3 provides a summary of these distinctions, highlighting their respective objectives, targeted systems, and the nature of compromised data.

III. ENERGY MARKET

A. MARKET EVOLUTION

The evolution of the electricity market has seen significant transitions in the reshaping of energy distribution and consumption. Initially, monopoly utilities managed the entire process, from generation to distribution within distinct regions. However, this centralization has faced efficiency and adaptability. The creation of power pools interconnected neighboring utilities through transmission networks, enabling cost-effective supply and enhanced reliability during high demand and emergencies. Despite these improvements, the full potential of interconnection was realized with the emergence of wholesale markets, which allowed real-time pricing and transactions, even if they initially overlooked transmission limitations. This has evolved into nodal markets, incorporating transmission constraints into pricing, leading to effective incentive structures and further innovation. LMPs have refined this approach by reflecting the marginal value of energy at specific times and locations, thus fostering efficient incentives and market optimization [1].

B. MARKET MODEL

Wholesale electricity markets are fundamental to the energy sector, enabling the exchange of electricity between produc-

ers and retailers. These markets are structured to guarantee efficient resource allocation, SG stability, and competitive pricing for consumers [1]. The key to a successful wholesale market model is to structure the real-time market according to LMPs that correspond to bid-based, security-constrained, and economic dispatch [24]. Wholesale markets have two main settlements: day-ahead and real-time. The day-ahead market allows market participants to trade electricity for delivery on the following day based on forecasts of supply and demand. However, the real-time market facilitates the adjustment of imbalances between actual and forecasted amounts [25].

1) Day-ahead Market

The day-ahead market operates in the short-term forward market. In this market, the load-serving entities and all generators submit their hourly anticipated demands and offer schedules 24 hours before the operation hour. The market operator then performs two essential procedures to derive the LMPs for each location in the system: Unit Commitment and Economic Dispatch [24]. Unit Commitment determines which generators are efficiently activated to meet demand, considering factors such as start-up costs and minimum up-time requirements. Economic Dispatch, however, focuses on minimizing operating costs while meeting demand by optimizing the power output of the activated units. Such an optimization process adheres to constraints such as the demand-supply balance, generator limits, and transmission-line capacities to ensure the security and reliability of the electrical grid.

2) Real-time Market

Real-time market operations are structured into two fundamental phases: ex-ante and ex-post. In the ex-ante phase, the system operator forecasts and schedules electricity generation to meet the anticipated demand based on the bidding prices submitted by different generation units prior to the actual operation. The subsequent ex-post phase deals with the final pricing settlement after the execution of actual operations. This settlement is based on the real-time operational conditions of the system [26], [27]. It is crucial to note that both phases are tightly coupled with the calculation of the LMPs, which reflect the marginal cost of supplying electricity at specific locations and times. Therefore, state estimation must be performed during this process to ensure accurate real-time pricing because inaccuracies in state estimates can result in substantial discrepancies in LMPs, potentially enabling manipulation.

State Estimation (SE) is a fundamental operation of various power system applications. It involves the processing of state variables and system state transitions, such as the bus voltage and bus angle. Data are collected from sensors that measure active and reactive bus power injections, branch power flows, and bus voltages [28]. The SE plays a key role in determining the LMPs for each node by providing the system operator with the necessary input to calculate the real-time operational state of the system. Through SE, the system operator makes

TABLE 3. Comparison of Financially Motivated Attacks in Smart Grid

	Energy Theft	LMPs Manipulation
Objective	Manipulating the billing system to avoid payment	Compromising state estimation to manipulate market outcomes
Attack origin	Often initiated from compromised end-user smart meters	Initiated from RTUs or similar system monitoring devices
Adversary	Typically consumers or prosumers seeking to avoid payment	Typically a market participant aiming for illegal profit gains
System	Affects the integrity of the distribution system	Affects the integrity of the transmission system
Market	Primarily impacts the retail market	Primarily impacts the wholesale market
Consequences	Results in monetary losses to distribution system operator	Leads to financial losses for other market participants, affecting market efficiency

informed technical and economic decisions, including congestion management, optimal power flow, and procurement of ancillary services [29], [30].

In the context of LMP manipulation, any inaccuracies in state estimation, or deliberate misrepresentation of system states, can affect the system's perceived congestion levels, and subsequently, the calculated LMPs. If a market participant can influence the state estimation process (e.g., by providing faulty data), it may be possible to artificially create congestion at specific locations, leading to inflated LMPs that benefit those manipulating the system.

In the EPS bus N_b , the sensor measurements obtained through SCADA relating to the optimal states are denoted as follows:

$$z = h(x, g) + \varepsilon, \quad (1)$$

where $h(\cdot, \cdot)$ represents the nonlinear relationship between measurements z and system states x within the SG topology (g), and ε signifies the inherent noise with covariance matrix \mathbf{R} . SE aims to infer a system state \hat{x} that best aligns with the measurements z , considering the influence of sampling noise in accordance with dependency h . Consequently, given the values of z , h , and \mathbf{R} , the system states are estimated by minimizing, for example, the Weighted Least Squares (WLS) method [28]:

$$\hat{x} = \arg \min_x (z - h(x))^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} (z - h(x)). \quad (2)$$

The minimization in (2) is obtained by adopting iterative approximation methods, such as Newton–Raphson [30].

The detection of erroneous data arising from faulty sensors or topological errors, can be performed using methods such as the Largest Normalized Residual (LNR) method [28]. According to this method, the estimated state variables \hat{x} are regarded as valid only when the norm of the measurement residuals falls below a predefined threshold value, denoted as γ , that is

$$\text{LNR} = \|z - h(\hat{x})\|^2 \leq \gamma. \quad (3)$$

However, if an adversary successfully alters the value of x while ensuring that Condition 3 still holds, they can effectively bypass the Bad Data Detection (BDD) mechanism. This allows the adversary to apply a FDIA stealthily, thereby compromising the system without detection. Further details of this attack are provided in Section IV.

The cost of operation in both ex-ante and ex-post markets involves determining a solution that optimally allocates power generation G_i to meet the expected load D_i , while ensuring compliance with physical security constraints at each EPS bus i . The generation cost c_i was calculated as follows [31]:

$$\min \sum_{i=1}^{N_b} c_i(G_i) \quad (4)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_b} (G_i - D_i) = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$P_i^{\min} \leq G_i \leq P_i^{\max} \quad \forall i \in N_b. \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_b} \text{GSF}_{l-i}(G_i - D_i) \leq F_l^{\max} \quad \forall l \in L. \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_b} \text{GSF}_{l-i}(G_i - D_i) \geq F_l^{\min} \quad \forall l \in L. \quad (8)$$

P_i^{\min} and P_i^{\max} represent the lower and upper generation capacities of the EPS bus i , respectively. The GSF_{l-i} refers to the generation shift factor matrix, whereas F_l^{\max} and F_l^{\min} are the upper and lower transmission capacities for line l , respectively.

δP_i^{\max} and δP_i^{\min} represent the upper and lower bounds, respectively, for the variations in generation. Therefore, the LMP on bus i is estimated as follows:

$$\text{LMP}_i = \lambda + \sum_{i=1} \text{GSF}_{l-i} \cdot \mu_l. \quad (9)$$

Here, λ is the Lagrange multiplier of the equality constraint in (5), and μ_l is the Lagrange multiplier of the l -th transmission constraint in (7) and (8). Notably, market operations rely heavily on real-time system constraints, which open vulnerabilities for attackers to falsify the transmission capacity reported to the control center without any actual or physical change. This has a direct impact on market operations, especially in real-time markets, where there is limited time to validate the data.

C. FINANCIAL TRADING IN ELECTRICITY MARKETS & TRANSMISSION RIGHTS

Financial trading in electricity markets involves leveraging price differentials and market fluctuations to profit from buying and selling electricity [32]. System operators facilitate this process by opening a market gateway where third parties, known as 'traders', engage in financial transactions to enhance market liquidity. These traders were neither generators nor consumers of electricity; they participated solely in financial transactions without handling actual electricity. The primary objective of a trader is to profit by purchasing electricity in the DA market and selling it in the RT market, or vice versa. It is crucial that any amount of electricity bought in the DA market is exactly sold back in the RT market [33]. Financial trading raise concerns for market operators, as traders may engage in market manipulation to maximize their profits [34].

Financial Transmission Rights (FTRs) are financial instruments that enable market participants to hedge against unforeseen changes in nodal prices and associated congestion charges [35]. These rights entitle the holder to a stream of revenue based on the price differences between specified nodes within the market. FTRs are crucial for managing price risk and ensuring price certainty for those involved in the production, distribution, and consumption of electricity. By securing FTRs, market participants efficiently forecast and stabilize their costs, thereby enhancing market efficiency and promoting investment in grid infrastructure. However, owing to the heavy dependence of SCED on transmission constraints, FTR holders can engage in LMP manipulation by reducing transmission capacity to create fictitious congestion for their benefit [36]. Further details are provided in Section IV.

IV. LMPs MANIPULATION THROUGH FDI ATTACKS

LMPs manipulation refers to unauthorized actions that compromise various underlying measurement units, such as RTUs and communication channels, to mislead LMPs in the energy market [37]. These stealthy activities are designed to avoid detection, bypass BDD, and persist over an extended period, thereby ensuring long-term gains for attackers [2]. They carried out FDIA and Man-in-the-Middle (MITM) attacks or their combination by malicious market participants. Although attacks on the center are unlikely because of strong security measures [38], an adversary is capable of manipulating the LMP by altering the system data reported to the control centre.

LMPs manipulation can be initiated by any market participant seeking to maximize benefits. The main actors in the energy market, include generators, demand-side participants, and financial traders. There are four primary scenarios for potential LMP manipulation: (i) a generator attempting to increase the LMP at their connected bus to boost revenue, (ii) a demand-side participant aiming to decrease the LMP at their connected bus to reduce costs, (iii) a financial trader striving to maximize the price difference between the selling

FIGURE 2. Number of publications per year.

FIGURE 3. Classification of attack and Defense studies, showing their proportions and relevant subcategories.

and purchase buses to optimize their financial gains, and (iv) any of the aforementioned participants with FTR profiting from the price differences across the two locations.

In recent years, there has been a noticeable increase in the literature addressing the problem of LMP manipulation through FDIA, with more than 70% of the reviewed studies focusing on this issue, as shown in Fig. 2. These attacks primarily target system data from various sources, including measurements, parameters, and topology, to mislead the state estimation. Such attacks constitute 80% of the analysed threat models, as depicted in Fig. 3. Other attack vectors, such as generation and load data alteration attacks and dispatch signal attacks, have also been found in the literature. This section provides a classification of existing threat models based on

their attack vectors, along with a theoretical explanation of the attack models and a state-of-the-art review of LMP manipulation threat models. Table 4 summarizes the technical details, categorized by attack type, attack vectors, and the knowledge required by attackers.

A. STATE ESTIMATION ATTACK

Measurement attacks aim to deceive SE processes and bypass BDD mechanisms, thereby significantly impacting dispatch operations and real-time LMPs. Manipulating measurements yields a one-time benefit, requiring repeated actions for subsequent LMP calculations [39]. Parameter and topology attacks target parameter processors and topology processors modules, allowing indirect modification of network parameters and topology datasets without accessing the highly secure control center. These attacks manipulate LMP calculations, ensuring long-term advantages for the adversaries [39]. A visual representation of these attacks is shown in Fig. 4.

1) Measurement Attack

Adversaries aim to execute FDIA by deceiving SE \hat{x} in (1) into a compromised estimated system state \hat{x}_a such that

$$\hat{x}_a = \hat{x} + c. \quad (10)$$

Factor c denotes the variation in the state of the targeted buses in the EPS. This manipulation was achieved by altering the measurements received at the control center to

$$z_a = z + a, \quad (11)$$

where a denotes the injected attack vector. To avoid detection through the BDD, the attack vector is defined as

$$a = h(\hat{x} + c) - h(\hat{x}). \quad (12)$$

In the scenario where the FDIA is constructed with complete knowledge of $h(\cdot)$ and g , the norm of the residual in 3 remains unaltered [59], that is,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LNR}_a &= \|z_a - h(\hat{x}_a)\| = \|z + a - h(x) - h(\hat{x} + c)\| \\ &= \|z - \hat{z}\| = \text{LNR}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Therefore, the manipulated measurements bypass the BDD without detection.

In scenarios with partial or no-prior knowledge, the attacker faces a trade-off between maximizing profit and remaining undetected by minimizing the value of γ . In the worst case where $\gamma = 0$, the attack becomes undetectable [60]. The concept of data integrity attacks in the energy market was first introduced in [34]. However, their approach assumed that the attacker had access to complete knowledge of the network topology and the optimal state. In realistic scenarios, it is impractical for an adversary to possess such information, given that EPSs data are vast, highly secure, and subject to dynamic changes owing to network topology adjustments in normal and contingency situations.

FIGURE 4. State Estimation Attack Paths through MITM and FDIA on RTU.

To address this limitation, subsequent research [42], [46], [48], [50], [51] developed FDIA models with partial knowledge of the SG. In [42], the authors proposed using linear independent component analysis (ICA) to infer the transmission line congestion status, thus, reducing the number of measurements that could be manipulated. In [48] and [51], attackers exploited historical data on the probability distributions of loads at different nodes across an SG. They employed Monte Carlo simulations to generate a range of expected power flow scenarios for the transmission lines. Zhang et al. [50] proposed an LMP manipulation without raising suspicion from market operators. This attack was designed to evade detection during the SE phase, while maintaining a normal LMP patterns. Mengis et al. [46] propose a worst-case robustness FDIA, where the attacker is capable of achieving profit while minimizing the value of γ in (3) to nearly zero.

Without prior knowledge of the SG topology and parameters, Tan et al. [44] designed online stealthy attacks that exploit online real-time streaming of measurements z . In their experiments, they achieved a large LMP deviation by implementing FDIA for data streaming in two measurements units.

2) Parameter Attack

The control center maintains a database of network parameters, including transformer tap settings, transmission line ratings, and branch admittances. However, these parameters may become inaccurate and obsolete over time owing to a lack of regular updates. To address this issue, the system operator initiates Network Parameter Error Processing (NPEP) to identify and correct errors in network parameters [61], [62].

The NPEP process comprises three main steps: (i) error identification, (ii) parameter estimation, and (iii) parameter updating. Given the actual SG parameters g in (1) and incorrect network parameters as \tilde{g} , in the presence of parameter errors, we can express the measurement model as follows:

$$z = h(x, \tilde{g}) + \varepsilon = h(x, g) + [h(x, \tilde{g}) - h(x, g)] + \varepsilon. \quad (14)$$

If \tilde{g} is sufficiently large, the LNR value surpasses the threshold γ in (3), thereby triggering a BDD alert.

TABLE 4. Current Threat Models for Energy Market Manipulation

Publication	Year	Scope	Attack Type	Attack vector	Attackers Knowledge
[34]	2011	Data integrity attacks in SE	Measurements attack	Set of measurements	Complete
[40]	2013	Stealthy MITM attack to falsify network topology	Cyber-topology attack	Breaker status	Complete
[41]	2013	Stealthily change ramp constraint limits to mislead LMP.	Generation data	Ramp-rate	Complete
[42]	2015	Stealthy FDIA in SE	Measurements attack	Voltage angle	Partial
[43]	2015	Bi-level optimization to maximize the attacker's profit	Parameter attack	Transmission line rating	Complete
[44]	2016	Online data integrity attack on real-time measurements	Measurements attack	Set of measurements	No prior knowledge
[45]	2017	FDIA attack to mislead the economic operations	Cyber-topology attack	Breaker status	Complete
[23]	2017	Coordinated cyber-topology attack to bypass NTP	Cyber-topology attack	Breaker status	Complete
[46]	2017	Worst-Case FDIA in DC network model	Measurements attack	Set of measurements	Partial
[47]	2017	Strategically curtailing generation power	Generation data	Output power	No prior knowledge
[48]	2018	FDIA to change the congestion patterns	Measurements attack	Power flow	Partial
[39]	2020	FDIA in SE to modify critical parameter	Parameter attack	Branch reactance	Complete
[49]	2020	FDIA in network parameter to reduce the number of attacked measurements	Parameter attack	phase angle & transformer tap ratios	Partial
[50]	2021	Stealthy FDIA in SE	Measurements attack	Power flow	Partial
[29]	2022	Coordinated cyber-physical attack to manipulate LMPs	Cyber-topology attack	Breaker status	Partial
[51]	2022	Monte Carlo-based FDIA strategy	Measurements attack	Power flow	Partial
[52]	2022	FDIA targeting AGC system	Dispatch signal attack	Dispatch signal	Complete
[53]	2023	Model-Measurement Data Integrity Attacks	Measurements attack	Set of measurements	Partial
[54]	2023	Using reinforcement learning to assess the vulnerability of LMP under cyber-topology attacks.	Cyber-topology attack	Breaker status	No prior knowledge
[55]	2023	Creating artificial high-loading conditions	Load altering attack	Load data	Partial
[56]	2024	Manipulating load data to influence the energy market	Load redistribution attack	Load data	Partial
[57]	2024	develop attack scenarios where attackers can manipulate data across multiple market transactions.	Measurements attack	Set of measurements	Complete
[58]	2024	Graph theory-based approach to identify critical measurements for launching FDIA.	Measurements attack	Set of measurements	Partial

Similar to the AC state estimation, NPEP estimate parameter \hat{g} as a WLS problem with the aim of minimizing the objective:

$$\hat{g} = \arg \min_g (z - h(x, g))^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} (z - h(x, g)). \quad (15)$$

In practice, processing measurements collected over multiple time frames significantly improves the accuracy of network parameter estimation [63]. Hence, any erroneous parameters stored in the database can be effectively rectified by updating them using more accurate estimates.

Attackers exploit vulnerabilities within the NPEP to indirectly manipulate the network parameter dataset, without requiring access to a securely protected control center [62]. This requires fewer capabilities, and can be executed offline. This leads to the manipulation of LMP calculations, thereby securing long-term benefits for the adversary. Well-designed parameter attacks pose challenges in detection due to their independence from the system operation points [39].

A study [43] examined the economic implications of Transmission Line Rating (TLR) attacks within two-settlement electricity markets, exploring how nodal prices in real-time markets can be manipulated through TLR attacks. In addition, the potential for cyber attackers to manipulate branch reactance and deceive LMP was explored in [39] and [38]. In [49], targeted transformer tap ratios and phase-shift angles were used to minimize the number of targeted measurements and introduce distortions into the outcomes of SE.

3) Cyber-Topology Attack

Cyber-topology attacks within EPSs focus on manipulating the network topology estimate. At the core of this manipulation is the Network Topology Processor (NTP), a critical element within the SCADA system that is instrumental in discerning connectivity statuses across the power network. NTP compiles data from various switching devices, such as circuit breakers, responsible for the connection or disconnection of the EPS components [45]. The network topology was

represented by an incidence matrix,

$$\mathbf{A}(q, p) \in [1, 0, -1]^{N_b \times L}, \quad (16)$$

where N_b is the number of buses and L is the number of transmission lines in an EPS. A transmission line connecting buses q and p is represented by 1 in the matrix, signifying the origin at bus q , and -1 denotes the termination at bus q . If there is no line connecting the two buses, it is denoted as zero. In a cyber-topology attack, an attacker can manipulate the cyber information sent to the control center, thereby altering the incidence matrix in (1). This, consequently affect the LMP calculations in SCED. For a successful cyber-topology attack, the attacker must also manipulate a set of measurements and bypass both the BDD and NTP to deceive the LMPs [45].

The impact of cyber-topology attacks on SCED solutions was studied in [45] and [23]. Undetectable cyber-topology attacks, as described in [40], conducted a MITM attack on the connection between the RTUs and the control center, affecting electricity prices in the wholesale market. In [29], a coordinated cyber-physical attack was proposed to manipulate an LMP. Reinforcement Learning was employed to assess the real-time electricity market vulnerability under cyber-topology attacks, where the attacker can modify the solution to the optimal-power-flow problem, thereby influencing LMPs with limited information about the grid topology structure [54].

B. DISPATCH SIGNAL

In addition to falsifying underlying measurements, malicious generators can further corrupt the dispatch signal by targeting the connection between the Automatic Generation Control (AGC) system and the generator unit [52]. AGC serves as a control mechanism used to adjust the output of generation resources in real-time, ensuring a balance between supply and demand while regulating the system frequency within acceptable limits. The attacker manipulates the signal to the generator to produce more energy, thereby generating illegal revenue at the expense of other generators in the same area [64].

C. GENERATION & LOAD DATA

The integrity of the generation and load data is crucial for ensuring the fairness and efficiency of the energy markets. Falsifying such data potentially enables market participants to manipulate market outcomes for financial gain. In [41], the authors explore false data injection attacks in real-time power markets using look-ahead dispatch models and propose strategies to manipulate generator ramp constraints for financial arbitrage through capacity withholding. In [47], they investigated potential market manipulation by aggregators of distributed generation in renewable energy-integrated power systems, focusing on strategically curtailing generation to maximize profit. In [55], Load Altering attacks were introduced, which created artificial high-loading conditions to sell energy at inflated prices. In [56], Load Redistribution attacks

were demonstrated by manipulating the line flow and load measurements in the SG to influence the energy market.

Highlights: This section classifies threat models related to energy market operations based on scope, attack type, attack vector, and the knowledge required to launch such attacks. Notably, most inputs to the LMP calculations can be manipulated without prior knowledge of the current state of the grid. In more sophisticated attacks, adversaries can adjust LMPs to align with expected patterns, complicating the detection of these manipulated prices. Additionally, while there is substantial research investigating SE FDIA, more studies are needed to explore FDIA in dispatch signals, generation data, and load data. More insights are provided in Section VI

V. LMPs MANIPULATION DEFENSE MECHANISMS

Limited research has been conducted on the detection of LMP manipulation. Most existing studies primarily focus on securing the SE process to ensure the reliability of higher-level applications, including economic decisions made at the market level. Consequently, current defense mechanisms are predominantly oriented towards either protecting the SE process or implementing detection techniques to identify anomalies in the data reported to the control center. This section provides an overview of the current state of research on LMP manipulation defense, categorizing the work into two main areas: protection and detection. Table 5 summarizes the defense strategies, detailing the publication year, defense level, and methods employed in each study.

A. PROTECTION STRATEGIES

In protection strategies, specific measurement units are identified as potential targets for malicious activities. Robust security measures are implemented to protect these selected units, including the optimized placement of the PMUs. PMUs provide precise measurements of electrical waveforms (voltage and current) in real-time with a high sampling rate and use GPS signals to synchronize their measurements across different locations. This ensures consistent and coherent data analysis [69]. Therefore, this feature makes PMUs exhibit resilience against data integrity attacks in comparison to RTUs, challenging attackers to manipulate measurements without raising suspicion of detection.

The study in [65] proposed a least-budget Defense strategy to protect pre-selected meters from the FDIA. The defense strategy is formulated as a mixed integer nonlinear programming problem, which is solved using Benders decomposition based on the most vulnerable system meters. In [66], a three-tier defender-attacker-operator methodology was proposed to simplify the process of identifying the minimum set of meters to protect to prevent market manipulation. In [69] and [70], the placement of PMUs was optimized to defend against data integrity attacks in power markets. Different strategies were used to identify the most vulnerable bus/branch and to determine the optimal number of PMUs to be deployed.

However, protection-based mechanism have certain limitations. First, it relies on the impractical assumption that PMUs

TABLE 5. Current Energy Market Defense Research

Publication	Year	Category	Defense Level	Method	Description
[44]	2016	Anomaly Detection	Control Level	Model-based	Use real-time measurements and baseline shift factor matrices to identify attacked measurements
[65]	2017	Protection using PMU	Physical Level	Game-theory	Define critical meters using Benders decomposition algorithm
[66]	2017	Protection using PMU	Physical Level	Model-based	Define critical meters using Three-tier defender-attacker-operator algorithm
[67]	2019	Anomaly Detection	Control Level	Model-based	Detection of the inconsistencies between network parameters and the historical measurements data
[68]	2020	Anomaly Detection	Control Level	Model-based	Detection of the variations in load and power flow
[50]	2021	Anomaly Detection	Market Level	Model-based	Differentiate safe and risky periods for detecting LMPs anomalies
[69]	2023	Protection using PMU	Physical Level	Optimization	Define critical buses/branches using Binary Harris Hawk optimization
[70]	2023	Protection using PMU	Physical Level	Optimization	Define critical buses/branches using a proposed algorithm to increase system observability
[62]	2023	Protection	Control Level	Model-based	Define minimal measurement set to detect changes in system parameters by analyzing both observability and Jacobian matrix
[71]	2024	Anomaly Detection	Market Level	Data-driven	Market-level integrated detection against cyber attacks in real-time market operations by self-supervised learning

are immune to attack. Indeed, PMUs are susceptible to GPS spoofing attacks, which can significantly affect the accuracy of their measurements [72]. Moreover, securing a subset of measurements reduces the level of data redundancy, thereby affecting SE accuracy [68].

B. ANOMALY DETECTION

In [62], the authors designed a detection strategy to identify malicious modifications of critical network parameters by analyzing the minimal protection set at a single branch. The algorithm proposed in [67] aims to detect cyberattacks by analyzing the inconsistencies between specified network parameters and historical data of power injections and voltage phasors. In [44], a detection algorithm using a shift factor matrix as a trustworthy baseline identified attacked real-time measurements. Improved SE approach that allow real-time detection of FDIA was presented in [68]. This method leverages Power Transmission Distribution Factors (PTDF) to calculate variations in load and power flow, aiming to detect indicators LMPs manipulation. In [50], a model using market-level data was proposed to differentiate between safe and risky periods for LMPs manipulation detection. These studies relied on statistical models for attack detection, with limitations in capturing complex and nonlinear system relationships, especially in the presence of sophisticated attacks [70]. Moreover, these techniques depend on utilizing historical data, limiting their ability to identify cyber-attacks when manipulated data are consistent with past measurements [68].

Highlights: This section explores the current defense mechanisms to protect energy market operations from manipulation. Protection strategies secure critical measurement units such as PMUs, whereas anomaly detection methods analyze data to identify signs of manipulation. However, research on defenses against market manipulation remains less

developed than the proposed threat models. This underscores the ongoing need for advanced anomaly detection models that can utilize multiple data sources to detect manipulated prices and identify the origin of attacks.

VI. CHALLENGES & FUTURE DIRECTIONS

A. POTENTIAL LMP MANIPULATION THREATS

Given the foundational role of LMP and SCED in market operations, inputs into SCED require careful scrutiny because of their potential vulnerabilities, which could be exploited to manipulate market prices and disrupt dispatch settlements. The threat posed by SE has been thoroughly examined in the literature (as discussed in Section IV). However, other types of attacks, such as those involving load altering attacks [55] and manipulations in load and generation forecasts [73], [74], remain largely unexplored in the context of their impact on market operations. Furthermore, the study of individual behaviors exhibited by DER owners, particularly concerning their bidding strategies and capacity withholding [41], represents an ongoing research frontier within the energy market context. The study and understanding of these less-explored attack vectors are important for fortifying the resilience of market mechanisms against potential manipulation and ensuring the reliability of EPSs. Furthermore, SG data analytics relies on a variety of machine learning applications to optimize their operations [75]. These applications encompass various functionalities, including resource scheduling, demand response forecasting, energy trading, and grid balancing. ML algorithms analyze historical data to make predictions, enabling efficient allocation of distributed energy resources and enhancing decision-making processes [76]. However, these ML applications are susceptible to adversarial ML attacks that have not yet been thoroughly investigated, particularly in the context of energy market manipulation. Adversarial

ML involves manipulating input data to deceive ML models, potentially leading to incorrect predictions or decisions [77], [78]. For example, adversarial attacks can compromise the accuracy of energy demand forecasts, disrupt resource scheduling, and manipulate trading strategies. Therefore, additional studies are necessary to explore the impact of adversarial ML on energy trading and develop ML models capable of detecting such attacks.

B. LMPS MANIPULATION DETECTION

As shown in Fig.3, there is a notable shortage of studies addressing LMP manipulation Defense, particularly in the area of LMP manipulation detection. Detection is a critical component of the market security. It provides a proactive mechanism to identify and respond to malicious activities before they escalate into significant financial or operational disruptions. Although protection mechanisms have been widely studied, they are inherently limited. These protection-centric approaches often involve reducing measurement redundancy [68], which can compromise the accuracy of state estimation (SE) results. Furthermore, protection-based mechanisms alone are insufficient for ensuring comprehensive security in market operations. A determined attacker can exploit vulnerabilities in these defenses, finding ways to corrupt or bypass them altogether. This highlights the importance of detection, as it complements protection by addressing scenarios in which safeguards fail.

A promising direction to addressing this gap is the development of data-driven detection models. These models leverage advanced machine learning and statistical techniques to analyze vast amounts of market and system-level data, identifying anomalous patterns indicative of manipulation. Unlike traditional model-based detection approaches that rely on pre-defined energy system models, data-driven models dynamically learn from historical and real-time data, improving their adaptability to emerging threats. Model-based approaches, although effective in capturing known attack scenarios, may struggle with novel or evolving manipulation techniques. In contrast, data-driven methods can detect subtle anomalies by leveraging complex correlations between system variables and market behaviors, thereby enhancing the detection accuracy. Moreover, incorporating market-level data is crucial for strengthening detection capabilities. Market data, such as nodal prices and transaction patterns, provides a broader perspective on system behavior beyond physical measurements. Time-series analysis of market data, when integrated with system-level data, allows for the identification of normal and abnormal market conditions, enabling the localization of attack origins and the recognition of their spatial effects across different node prices. Despite its potential, the application of market-level data for LMP manipulation detection remains largely unexplored, creating a significant research gap that warrants further investigation and development to enhance cybersecurity in the energy market.

Furthermore, the effectiveness of the LMP manipulation detection can be significantly enhanced by deploying real-

time detection models. Given the dynamic nature of energy markets, where price fluctuations and system conditions evolve rapidly, real-time detection is essential to provide timely alerts and mitigation strategies. Traditional post-event analysis methods, which are valuable for forensic investigations, lack the immediacy required to prevent market disruptions and financial loss. Real-time detection models, driven by streaming data analytics and edge computing, enable the continuous monitoring of market activities, allowing for instant anomaly detection and rapid response. Various techniques, including adaptive thresholding, online learning, and event-driven architectures, help quickly identify suspicious activities and activate automated countermeasures to mitigate threats before they spread. Moreover, integrating real-time detection systems with market operator control frameworks can provide actionable intelligence, ensuring a more resilient and secure electricity market.

C. UTILIZING MULTIPLE DATA SOURCES

Several studies have demonstrated that an increased number of data sources significantly enhances the accuracy of market manipulation detection [21]. We argue that integrating diverse datasets, including weather, measurement, and market data, can effectively yield robust detection results in the context of financially motivated attacks. The combination of these varied data types not only enriches the analytical framework but also contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the complex patterns associated with LMP manipulation. Hence, this point opens an important research direction that could contribute significantly to the detection of financially motivated attacks in the energy market.

D. NEED FOR LMPS ANOMALY DETECTION DATASET

Developing an LMP anomaly detection dataset is crucial for advancing the research on energy market integrity and resilience. Current datasets focus on normal historical LMPs, which, while useful for understanding market behavior, lack the support of effective anomaly detection. Additionally, existing anomaly detection datasets primarily focus on system measurements, potentially missing crucial market dynamics. To bridge these gaps, future datasets should encompass a diverse range of scenarios and market conditions, including normal operations and anomalous behaviors such as price spikes or prolonged deviations. This broader scope should integrate contextual factors such as weather data, demand patterns, and market events alongside LMP values to enhance dataset robustness and provide a comprehensive context for interpreting anomalies. Annotated instances of known manipulation or market disturbances are essential for training robust detection models that support both supervised learning approaches and unsupervised anomaly detection methods. Granularity in temporal and spatial dimensions is critical for the effective detection and localization of anomalies across different scales within the energy grid. This approach ensures that anomalies can be promptly and accurately identified,

contributing to enhanced market transparency and resilience against manipulation.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The increasing integration of digital technologies in energy markets has introduced new vulnerabilities, making them susceptible to sophisticated cyberattacks, particularly FDIAs. Our review highlights a diverse range of attack vectors that can manipulate LMPs and disrupt market stability and financial fairness. While existing defenses primarily focus on securing state estimation and anomaly detection, they remain limited in addressing the broader market-level impact of FDIAs. Our study highlights the need for a more holistic approach that incorporates market-level data analytics, multi-source information fusion, and advanced machine learning techniques for real-time detection. Additionally, adversarial attacks on predictive models and market forecasting remain largely unexplored, presenting a critical research gap. Addressing these challenges requires the development of robust anomaly detection datasets and the integration of cross-disciplinary insights to enhance energy market resilience, ensuring both security and market integrity in an increasingly digitalized landscape.

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